

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

OPPORTUNITIES OF HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT IN THE FIELD OF PROVIDING DIGITAL LABORATORY ANALYSES THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract

Currently, the professional work of the medical sector feels numerous changes, including the influence of technological innovations. This process occurs very quickly, significant changes can be observed during the life of just one generation. A huge complex of modern information technologies very clearly demonstrates the direction and stages of development of global informatization processes throughout the world, and their holistic impact on the economic and scientific-technical parts of modern society causes serious changes in the usual sectors of the economy and all other spheres of everyday life of each of us.

Keywords: Digitalization, healthcare, digital laboratories, management in healthcare, digitalization of healthcare

The digital transformation of the healthcare system is revolutionizing the way healthcare is delivered, making it more accessible, efficient, and personalized for patients. However, it is important to ensure that privacy and security measures are in place to protect sensitive medical information and maintain trust in the system. Digital technologies have become a significant factor in transformation in all areas, from management, production to agriculture and medicine. The development of laboratory diagnostics in our country can be used to clearly trace aspects of the informatization of modern medicine.

Telemedicine has become increasingly popular, allowing patients to receive medical consultations and even treatments remotely without having to physically visit a healthcare facility. This not only saves time and money for patients but also helps in reducing the burden on healthcare facilities.

Additionally, the use of wearable technology and health monitoring devices has enabled individuals to track their health metrics and share this information with healthcare professionals, leading to more personalized and effective treatment plans. This has the potential to improve preventive care and help individuals manage chronic conditions more effectively.

Furthermore, artificial intelligence and data analytics are being used to improve decision-making in healthcare, leading to more accurate diagnoses and treatment plans. Machine learning algorithms can analyze large datasets to identify patterns and trends that can help in predicting and preventing diseases.

Clinical laboratory diagnostics is engaged in the development and use of various methods for diagnosing diseases, and monitors their course. Thanks to the availability of a large set of analytical equipment, it allows a clinician to assess metabolic disorders in the human body and significantly simplify diagnosis, select a qualified treatment regimen and assess the prognosis for many pathologies.

Today, laboratory diagnostics is one of the most rapidly developing medical specialties. Highly informative diagnostic and therapeutic methods are being

developed and introduced into clinical practice. It was only recently that laboratory technologies were just beginning to appear, and manual research methods were gradually entering medical practice, but at this stage they are regularly being improved and enriched with new modern diagnostic approaches. Increasing their specificity and sensitivity contributes to the expansion of the objects of analysis. For diagnostic purposes, in addition to traditional urine and blood serum testing, cerebrospinal fluid, exhaled air condensate, vaginal discharge, etc. are increasingly used [1, p. 4].

In recent years, high-tech modern systems for analyzing peripheral blood have been created, which are practically replacing manual and semi-automatic research methods. They certainly have a number of advantages, among which are the wide analytical capabilities of hematological analyzers, a small volume of blood for analysis (12–150 μ), high productivity (up to 100–120 samples per hour), analysis of a large number (tens of thousands) of cells, evaluation of 18–30 or more parameters simultaneously, graphical presentation of research results in the form of histograms, but most importantly – high accuracy and reproducibility of the study, since several tens or even hundreds of thousands of cells of one sample are counted [2, p. 561].

The structure of the clinical laboratory service of our country includes a widely ramified network of various healthcare institutions: from republican and regional healthcare organizations (regional and city hospitals) to rural district hospitals and medical outpatient clinics, as well as specialized laboratories.

Modern biochemical research in laboratories is fully automated. The following is carried out automatically:

- sample preparation;
- analysis using conductometry, laser light scattering and laser fluorocytometry;
- displaying readings on the monitor in digital form and using graphs and histograms;
- processing and storing information;

- internal contamination testing, automatic system flushing, aperture cleaning with ultrasound [3, p. 3782].

Automation allowed the hematological blood analyzer has high productivity, which allows you to do a complete blood count in a matter of minutes, without which correct diagnosis and effective therapy are impossible.

The widespread introduction of biological material analyzers allows for complex analysis with a smaller sample volume, which significantly speeds up and simplifies the diagnostic procedure. Thanks to the creation of a sufficiently powerful production base in our country to produce clinical laboratory products, laboratories are equipped with the necessary equipment, as well as diagnostic reagent kits. The introduction of information technology in laboratory diagnostics has made it possible to carry out a huge range of studies using a domestic reagent base and on our own equipment.

Overall, we are already seeing a trend towards making diagnostics and health care more accessible at home, and self-treatment is also developing. Here are some factors that contribute to the creation of a home laboratory.

Advances in technology make it possible to create compact and affordable medical devices that allow for home health diagnostics and monitoring. As noted above, these include devices such as glucometers, thermometers, cardiographs, blood pressure monitors, miniature «Holters», ultrasound scanners, etc.

Mobile applications and telemedicine platforms provide patients with the opportunity to diagnose diseases remotely [4, p. 323]. This is especially convenient for those who live in remote areas or have limited mobility.

With individual devices and mobile applications, patients can self-monitor their health, track important indicators, and receive personalized care recommendations. This allows them to actively participate in managing their health and prevent potential problems.

The introduction of an integrated electronic medical record (IEMR) allows the patient to receive a full-fledged personal PHR (Personal Health Records) card with a history of examinations and treatment, supplemented by the patient's own observations, examinations and self-monitoring results, which can significantly facilitate the work of doctors [5, p. 571].

The Internet and mobile applications provide patients with broad access to information about diseases, symptoms, treatment methods and prevention. This allows them to better understand their health and make informed decisions about their lifestyle and treatment.

Despite some advantages of self-diagnosis and self-treatment, it is important to remember that some diseases require professional medical intervention, and self-diagnosis may not be accurate enough, and sometimes even harmful. Therefore, it is important to use such technologies wisely and, if necessary, seek help from doctors.

Given the trend of diagnostics and health care becoming more accessible at home, as well as the development of self-medication, it is important for

healthcare organizations to develop a strategy that will correspond to these changes. Here are some key aspects that healthcare organizations can consider in their strategy.

It is important to train medical personnel in the use of new telemedicine technologies and platforms, as well as to provide support and training to patients on the use of individual devices and mobile applications for self-monitoring and health care.

Healthcare organizations must ensure a high level of protection and confidentiality of medical data, especially when using telemedicine services and transferring data between patients and doctors.

Medical organizations can prepare home care services, organize the collection of biomaterials for subsequent studies, the delivery of devices and medicines, and other activities necessary for high-quality patient care. At the same time, strict protocols, regulations, and procedures must be developed and implemented to control the quality and safety of the technologies and services being implemented [6, p. 640].

These activities will help healthcare organizations successfully adapt to changes in patient preferences and needs due to the development of home diagnostics and self-treatment, as well as effectively use new technologies to improve the quality and accessibility of healthcare.

The development of home care and delivery of various devices, materials, and medical services is a particularly important aspect of the strategy of healthcare organizations in the context of the development of home diagnostics and self-treatment. Let us highlight several reasons why this is important:

Providing home services ensures the provision of medical care without the need to visit a clinic.

In the context of epidemics and pandemics, home care and delivery of medical services can help reduce the risk of infection and the spread of infections, since patients do not need to leave home to receive medical care.

Home care provides convenience and comfort for patients, especially for those who need regular medical monitoring or treatment. It also allows patients to be closer to their family and surrounding environment, which can contribute to their psychological well-being and recovery.

Healthcare organizations can provide a variety of services at home, such as medical consultations, treatment procedures, medical tests, physical therapy, and rehabilitation, allowing them to expand their range of services and attract new patients. Home care can help healthcare organizations optimize resource utilization, as it allows them to better allocate staff and equipment, reduce rental costs, and improve operational efficiency.

With the rise of self-medication and the use of new technologies in medicine, some specializations of healthcare personnel may become more in demand. Here are a few specializations that may become more important:

General practitioners/family doctors will play an important role in self-medication, as they will be the first point of contact for most patients [7, p. 18]. They

should be prepared to educate patients on the use of mobile apps to manage their health, as well as provide consultations on diagnostics and treatment at home.

Medical assistants and nurses will play an important role in helping patients use medical devices and apps, perform home procedures, and monitor their health. They can also provide educational programs and instructions to patients.

Doctors and healthcare workers specializing in telemedicine will be in demand to conduct remote consultations with patients, as well as to develop and implement telemedicine platforms and programs.

Data processing and analytics specialists who analyze patient data, predict diseases, as well as evaluate the effectiveness of self-medication methods and make decisions based on the results.

With the increasing number of patients managing their own health, there is a growing need for health educators to develop educational materials, training programs, and coaching for patients on how to use medical devices, apps, and self-care methods.

The digital transformation in healthcare, based on digital innovations and increased self-diagnosis and home treatment, is shifting towards a more accessible, personalized and efficient healthcare model. New technologies such as mobile health apps, telemedicine platforms and self-monitoring devices are becoming more common among patients, allowing them to be more actively involved in their health care.

In the context of self-diagnosis and home treatment of the population, the demand for telemedicine, data analytics and health education specialists will increase, as they will play a key role in supporting patients and providing quality medical care at a remote level.

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